

Taxonomic Binning of samples by SampleID

16S with NA

- Genus
- g__Acidibacter
 -
 g__ADurb.Bin063-1
 -
 g__Anaerolinea
 -
 g__Anaeromyxobacter
 -
 g__Azospirillum
 -
 g__Bradyrhizobium
 -
 g__Brevinema
 -
 g__Bryobacter
 -
 g__Candidatus_Koribacter
 -
 g__Candidatus_Phytoplasma
 -
 g__Candidatus_Solibacter
 -
 g__Christensenellaceae_R-7_group
 -
 g__Dongia
 -
 g__Geobacter
 -
 g__Haliangium
 -
 g__Lacunisphaera
 -
 g__Leptolinea
 -
 g__Methylocystis
 -
 g__MND1
 -
 g__NA
 -
 g__Quadrisphaera
 -
 g__Rhizomicrobium
 -
 g__Ruminiclostridium
 -
 g__Sideroxydans
 -
 g__Sphingomonas
 -
 g__Spirochaeta
 -
 g__Tolimonas
 -
 g__Treponema
 -
 g__UTCFX1
 -
 g__WCHB1-32
 -
 Other

Taxonomic Binning of samples by SampleID

16S without NA

Genus

- g__Acidibacter
- g__ADurb.Bin063-1
- g__Anaerolinea
- g__Anaeromyxobacter
- g__Azospirillum
- g__Bradyrhizobium
- g__Brevinema
- g__Bryobacter
- g__Candidatus_Koribacter
- g__Candidatus_Phytoplasma
- g__Candidatus_Solibacter
- g__Christensenellaceae_R-7_group
- g__Dongia
- g__Geobacter
- g__Haliangium
- g__Lacunisphaera
- g__Leptolinea
- g__Methylocystis
- g__MND1
- g__Paludibaculum
- g__Quadrisphaera
- g__Rhizomicrobium
- g__Ruminiclostridium
- g__Sideroxydans
- g__Sphingomonas
- g__Spirochaeta
- g__Tolomonas
- g__Treponema
- g__UTCFX1
- g__WCHB1-32
- Other

Taxonomic Binning of samples by SampleID

18S root and rhizo

Genus

- g__Acidibacter
 - g__ADurb.Bin063-1
 - g__Anaerolinea
 - g__Anaeromyxobacter
 - g__Azospirillum
 - g__Bradyrhizobium
 - g__Brevinema
 - g__Bryobacter
 - g__Candidatus_Koribacter
 - g__Candidatus_Phycoplasmata
 - g__Candidatus_Solibacter
 - g__Christensenellaceae_R-7_group
 - g__Dechloromonas
 - g__Dongia
 - g__Geobacter
 - g__Haliangium
- g__Lacunisphaera
 - g__Leptolinea
 - g__Methylocystis
 - g__MND1
 - g__Quadriflora
 - g__Rhizomicrobium
 - g__Ruminiclostridium
 - g__Sideroxydans
 - g__Sphingomonas
 - g__Spirochaeta
 - g__Tolomonas
 - g__Treponema
 - g__UTCFX1
 - g__WCHB1-32
 - Other

Taxonomic Binning of samples by SampleID

18S Roots

- Genus
- g__Aphanochaete
 - g__Bursaria
 - g__Cercomonadidae_g1
 - g__Chaetomium
 - g__Chaetoniopsis
 - g__Chronogaster
 - g__Cryptomycotha_g1
 - g__Dorylaimida_g1
 - g__Dorylaimida_g2
 - g__Endogonales_g1
 - g__Flamella
 - g__Haplotaxida_g1
 - g__Hirschmanniella
 - g__Kerriona
 - g__Kraken
 - g__Meloiodogyne
 - g__Metopus
 - g__Monoblepharella
 - g__Navicula
 - g__Nowakowskiella
 - g__Paracercomonas
 - g__Pinnularia
 - g__Plasmodiophora
 - g__Plectus
 - g__Pristina
 - g__Pythium
 - g__Rhizoctonia
 - g__Rhogostoma
 - g__Septochytrium
 - g__Vermamoeba
 - Other